

RESEARCH ON BUDDHIST ECONOMIC MODEL: PRACTICE IN VIETNAM

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Buddhist Economics is a new field of study that has only emerged in recent years. In the context of globalization today, researchers often propose economic models that are sustainable, equitable, and ethical in business. Some views hold that economics in Buddhism is only a religious ideology, not practical for modern society, or can only develop in countries where Buddhism is the dominant religion. However, reality proves that Buddhist economics is closely related to many other industries and fields, not only in the economic field but also in harmoniously solving social, personal, and environmental problems with a symbiotic approach. The article synthesizes some theoretical foundations of Buddhism and presents some current situations of Buddhist economic development in Vietnam.

Keywords: Economics, Buddhism, theory, practice, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

“Right Livelihood” is the first and most important issue in the Noble Eightfold Path of the Buddha, so it is necessary to have in-depth studies on Buddhist economics. Some countries that take Buddhism as their national religion are often very loyal to the beliefs and heritage left by their ancestors, while at the same time they are steadfast in developing the economy in a modern direction, with the mindset that there is no contradiction between religious values and economic progress. We can see that spiritual health and material development are not different but closely related. Many opinions say that a Buddhist-oriented lifestyle does not need Buddhist economic thinking. Developing from a Buddhist perspective, economics is not isolated from other issues but is an indispensable part of the effort to solve basic human problems. Economics based on Buddhist foundations is part of a whole range of sciences that contribute to solving individual, social and environmental problems towards the goal of sustainable development.

The Buddhist perspective focuses on the advantages, disadvantages and benefits of human activities related to production and business, guiding us to mature in business ethics. It shows us that people who want to survive must work hard, worry about their own lives and their families. It educates everyone to know how to spend for daily life and save a part to prepare for unexpected events in emergencies (Stock up food to prepare for emergencies) and production and business. With such teachings, it helps everyone to be economically stable, have capital to invest in production and business, and also helps people change their thinking and perception in economic development such as: if you want a peaceful and liberated life, the economy must be stable, develop sustainably and harmoniously. Buddhism takes compassion as the top priority, not seeking personal gain at the expense of others, thereby creating a good lifestyle that does not harm the interests of others for the purpose of increasing personal profit.

2. Buddhist economic concepts

The basic principles of Buddhist economics are rooted in the ancient teachings of the Buddha, but the term Buddhist economics has only emerged in the last half century. The book “Small is Beautiful: A study of

Economics as if people mattered” by British economist E.F. Schumacher. The term “Buddhist economics” was coined by him in 1955 when he was an economic adviser to the Prime Minister of Myanmar. Buddhist economics was later published in “Asia: A handbook” in 1966 and in 1973 was included in Schumacher’s influential collection “Small is Beautiful: A study of Economics as if people mattered”. Buddhist economics is primarily a reflection of the Buddhist understanding of economic development. In his commentary on Buddhist economics, Schumacher begins with the “Noble Eightfold Path” of Buddhist teachings. He examined the legitimacy of modern economic activities from one of the “Noble Eightfold Path” of Buddhism, which is “right livelihood”. He emphasized that “right livelihood” is the right way of life or the right way of life, which is essential for a Buddhist economics. This is also an important starting point in Schumacher’s argument. He also demonstrated that the idea of “the middle way” has extremely important value in economics. “It is not wealth but the obstinate pursuit of wealth that hinders liberation, it is not the enjoyment of pleasures but the craving for them that hinders liberation,” he argued. “Thus the main aim of Buddhist economics is simplicity and nonviolence.” The book, dubbed the “ecological bible” by Time magazine [3], became a landmark statement against “bigger is better” industrialism and was ranked as one of the 100 most influential books published after World War II.

Although rooted in Buddhism, the principles of Buddhist economics aim to solve universal problems, not isolated in religious ideology but towards solving social, personal and environmental problems in a harmonious way. This shows that the scope of potential application of Buddhist economics has gone beyond the Buddhist community, positioning it as a philosophy of Moral Economics.

Interdependence: This principle recognizes that all beings and phenomena are interconnected. From an economic development perspective, attention must be paid to the impact on society and the environment, and to cooperation, altruism, and collective responsibility rather than selfish competition.

Sustainability: Buddhist economics also helps to realize that resources are limited and therefore the need

to develop the economy in harmony with nature. It supports sustainable development projects that minimize environmental damage and protect ecosystems for the future, such as enhancing ecosystem regeneration and prudent use of non-renewable resources, thus the destruction of natural resources is seen as contrary to this principle while green growth policies are seen as similar to this philosophy.

Moderation/Simplicity: This principle directs people to control their desires and avoid overconsumption. The goal is not to maximize consumption but to “achieve maximum well-being with minimum consumption”. Simplicity is seen as the key to reducing suffering and freeing up time and energy for increased creativity. This involves distinguishing between *taṇhā* (craving, blind desire for objects of pleasure) and *chanda* (righteous desire for well-being).

Well-being over Profit: The goal of Buddhist economics is not to maximize profits but to maximize well-being – including material, mental, social and spiritual – and to minimize suffering for all beings. Profit and material wealth are seen as means, not ends in themselves, with this approach placing greater importance on non-material values, such as the joy of giving or the wisdom gained from practice.

Right Livelihood: This is an important element in the Noble Eightfold Path, the path to enlightenment according to the teachings of Buddhism. The presence of Right Livelihood in the Noble Eightfold Path is the foundation of Buddhist economics, because it indirectly refers to the economic aspect of life. Right Livelihood is a way of living that is lawful, honest, and does not harm others. The Buddha has identified five types of businesses that should be avoided: 1/ arms trading, 2/ human trafficking (including slavery and prostitution), 3/ meat production and trading (involving killing), 4/ trading in intoxicants (such as alcohol), 5/ trading in poison. Practicing Right Livelihood is the foundation for building a moral, meaningful life, bringing peace and inner peace. Today, the concept of Right Livelihood is extended to a livelihood based on liberation, with this approach not only limiting harm but also emphasizing self-nurturing, self-care, the ability to express one's talents through work, and finding work that is deeply meaningful and makes a positive contribution to the world..

Comparison between Buddhist economics and basic economics

Characteristic	Buddhist economics	Basic economics
Main objective	Maximize total well-being, minimize suffering	Maximize utility, profit, GDP
Unit of analysis	Interdependent system (individual-society-environment)	The rational, autonomous individual ("homo economicus")
Human nature	Interdependent, capable of altruism, influenced by <i>taṇhā</i> (craving, which needs to be controlled and reduced) and <i>chanda</i> (righteous desire for well-being)	Rational, self-interest maximization, unlimited desires
Lust	Distinguishing <i>taṇhā</i> (need to reduce) and <i>chanda</i> (need to cultivate); aiming at simplicity	Infinite desires, to be satisfied through consumption
Labor	Means of human development, with intrinsic value	Maximize benefits, production costs
Consumption	Means for welfare; goal: optimal (sufficient)	End in itself; goal: maximization
Value	Based on contribution to real and moral welfare	Based on utility and scarcity
Resources	Precious natural capital needs to be managed sustainably	Factors of production, which are substitutable, environmental issues are "externalities"
Morality	Inseparable	Often self-identified as "positive", non-judgmental
Philosophy	Dependent Origination, Middle Way, Right Livelihood, Non-violence	Utilitarianism, Methodological Individualism

This comparison table shows us the similarities in approach and basic priorities, showing that Buddhist economics is not just a transformation of modern economics but a system of ethical thinking in current economics.

3. Practice of Buddhist economic development in Vietnam

Buddhist ideology has contributed to adjusting human behavior and attitudes towards nature and society, which is a very important factor determining the pros-

perity and sustainability of a country's economy. Buddhist ideology has contributed to creating motivation for the exploitation and rational use of resources in the growth and sustainable development of the economy in Vietnam. According to Buddhist philosophy, resources must be fully utilized to avoid waste in the use of resources, which is "parasitism" in society. Labor helps people survive in life, this is an ideology that helps people respect resources in society more. Buddhist ideology focuses on the value and talent of people, the importance of the ecosystem, the depletion of resources

and offers solutions instead of exploiting and controlling nature. People will use their knowledge and talents to produce and exploit reasonably, while protecting, caring for and nurturing nature. Buddhism supports the goal of not harming the environment. Especially when the environment is seriously polluted, countries are moving towards a green economy and a circular economy.

Buddhism is contributing to the development of the spiritual tourism economy, the tangible and intangible values associated with religious works in Vietnam are pagodas, temples and religious cultural works associated with relics that are the target objects of spiritual tourism. Spiritual cultural tourism in Vietnam is associated with the worship, gratitude, and gratitude of national heroes, predecessors who have contributed to the country and the nation (Thanh Hoang) becoming tourism to the national origin with the morality of drinking water and remembering its source.

Buddhist establishments have contributed to the state in implementing social security, contributing to stabilizing the political economy. Buddhist establishments have opened free vocational training classes and introduced free jobs to thousands of students to help reduce the unemployment rate in society and create jobs for workers. Vietnam is not outside the general vortex of the world, however, the development of Buddhist human resources in economic development in some large pagodas in Vietnam has many multi-dimensional views. In the process of developing the Buddhist economy in Vietnam, there are still some issues as follows:

- Prevent the commercialization of Buddhism:

According to the traditional view, Buddhism needs to be pure and free from worldly dust, but the process of Buddhism entering society constantly poses challenges to the traditional view of Buddhism. That is to create favorable conditions for the acceptance of Buddhist teachings by sentient beings, such as reducing strict rituals, making the method of preaching and propagating the Dharma more flexible and more suitable for modern life), while some challenges have negative impacts on Buddhism, such as economic problems in some Buddhist places of worship. The assets of monks need to be carefully resolved, because the Buddhist Sangha is an organization pursuing liberation for themselves and sentient beings, if it creates too great a challenge to this point, it is very dangerous for the development of Buddhism. Moreover, the process of secularizing Buddhism is bringing monastic life closer to the life of enjoyment of the market economy, chasing after material values. Therefore, it leads to negative phenomena such as selling gods and saints, superstition... weakening the faith of Buddhist followers in the path to liberation in Buddhism. Some Buddhist establishments are built large and beautiful in many different localities, but the spiritual quality is gradually fading, some establishments are secularized and commercialized, unable to maintain their inherent purity. Therefore, secularization without being transformed by secularization is always an issue that Buddhism needs to face. No matter how fast the Buddhist economy develops, it cannot lose the essence of Theravada Buddhism. The purpose of developing the Buddhist economy is not to lose the essence

of Buddhism, they integrate into the philosophy of Buddhism to develop the cause of propagating the Dharma to benefit humanity, education, culture, and humanity instead of making profits from a large-scale economic entity. This is an issue that needs to be studied in the balance of the relationship between the Buddhist economy and the Buddhist precepts.

- giáo Identify the economic motives of Buddhism

These activities are usually economic and religious activities. Economic activities in temples are mainly the operations of the monastic economy such as production, agricultural labor, providing accommodation services for tourists and pilgrims. These are very necessary activities but do not affect the monastic life of monks and, importantly, do not affect Buddhism in propagating the Dharma and benefiting sentient beings. Religious activities are essentially professional activities of monks and nuns, but to varying degrees they have become activities to seek benefits, so this is the focus for analyzing economic motives. When Buddha was still alive, he taught his disciples: "To keep the precepts, monks must not trade, sell, barter, buy land and houses, raise people, servants and animals, take care of planting, and trade in treasures. Avoid all of these things like avoiding a fire pit" (WangTi, 1999). Even "cutting down trees and digging the ground. Making medicine, fortune telling, astrology, weather prediction, and calendar calculations are not suitable for monks" (Di Giao Sutra). Accordingly, what is suitable for monks is "to be self-disciplined and mindful" (Guang Jian, 2020). Buddhism has many resources for development such as through ritual activities, but the excessive pursuit of resources and material things has violated the original thoughts of the Buddha. The Buddha once predicted when he interpreted a dream for Ananda before he died: "The monks in the future will sell the Tathagata out of greed for profit and increased income, and they will use the sutras as a means of making a living" (Wang Ti, 1999). Buddhist economics always exists objectively, but how to direct their economic motivation to change into an economic motivation for the benefit of sentient beings.

- Challenges in the modernization of Buddhism:

The document of the 13th National Congress of the Party affirmed: "Promoting good cultural and ethical values and resources of religions for the cause of national development" (Communist Party of Vietnam, 2021, vol. 1, p. 171). In the present era, Buddhism is a major religion in Vietnam, with many followers, so Buddhism is increasingly becoming a religion with great potential in both material and spiritual terms. The impact of the economy on Buddhism, such as when the economy develops, society provides more material wealth to Buddhism, can also lead Buddhism to worship money and material things or can create the risk of moral degradation within the organization, causing monks to lose their hearts. This not only affects the personal practice of Buddhism but also greatly damages the image of Buddhism. Therefore, we need to face the challenge of modernizing the Buddhist economy. This is also the trend that needs to be prevented so that Buddhism can both propagate the Dharma and expand its

influence in society, but at the same time still maintain its value and not be distorted.

Conclusion

Buddhism has contributed to sustainable economic development, Buddhism's activities in economic development are extremely practical, however, there must be certain solutions to further strengthen that role of Buddhism. Buddhist economics demonstrates efforts in solving behaviors in human life. Therefore, we need to balance culture and ethics. Sustainable development is associated with environmental friendliness. Currently, in response to the requirement of promoting industrialization and modernization of the country, developing the socio-economy in parallel with strengthening national defense and security, continuing to further promote the strength of the great national unity bloc. Because religion always directs people towards truth, goodness and beauty, in the new context, Buddhist

thoughts need to be adjusted to suit the integration process but must maintain the values of tradition.

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